

NSF Racial Equity > Environmental Justice Matters

The Url for this page is

<https://bit.ly/EnvironmentalJusticeMatters>

We are working on our *in-progress NSF Proposal* > Deadline date is the 8th of October 2024 for the Full Proposal.

Our collaboration is Stephen Fischer MD MPH, Sherrish Holloman EdD, and Kevin Moses JD PhD.

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We researched and consulted [Google > Gemini](#) on publishing the drafts of our Proposal:

Here is Gemini on some of the reasons why it is not a good idea to publish to public view your progress drafts of an NSF Proposal:

- * It could jeopardize your chances of getting funding.*
- * It could give away your research ideas to competitors.*
- * It could violate the NSF's confidentiality policy.*
- * It could damage your reputation.*

We agree and are implementing Gemini's guidance. Our experimentation with Artificial Intelligence(AI) > Gemini and the OpenAI gpt-4 python library will be recorded in our '*internal register*'.

Our collaboration with an AI research assistant, is primarily via a Google Colab Notebook running a GPT-4 library ... we interpreted this as a beautiful rendering. I(KM) am a fan of the programming language Python. It is fast, making it a good choice for high-performance applications. Tryouts with ChatGPT-3.5 are in my (KM) teaching practice: *Supplement 3 of 'Designing > Assignment_1d > Large Language Models and Imaginative Reasoning in the Classroom Space.'* 9 Feb. 2023, <https://zenodo.org/record/7811747> > Get the latest PDF here: https://zenodo.org/record/8372150/files/ChatGPTReasoning_202309231002.pdf?download=1. I updated Supplement 3, created a separate note, and hosted it here <https://bit.ly/TheAIregister>. Our plans:

- On designing for the future > build an AI *internal register*.
 - Our upgrade to our practice includes a commitment to maintaining an *internal register*.
- We all teach, and our practice includes a disclosed *register* for our classroom space where we publish AI's response to our assignments and questions. ***AI is another player for that space.***
- During the Spring 2023 Semester: I(KM) promoted ***#ArtificialIntelligence (AI)*** as a collaborating research assistant, asking course members to credit *the AI work product*. A micro-debate in class was on AI as a curator of existing info., not a creator, some members agreed, and some disagreed. ... I started a ***#Bard*** conversation on this issue,

You: Question_on_Novel: Bard you have previously written that The word "generative" in the context of Bard means "creating something new." ... Is this accurate, I see Bard as a curator not a creator of the new and novel. I am using 'novel' following a lineage developed in US Patent Law. Is my interpretation accurate?

Bard: I see your point. In the context of US patent law, "novel" means that an invention is new and non-obvious. In this sense, Bard is not a creator of the new and novel, because it generates text that is based on existing text. However, I would argue that Bard is still a generative AI, because it can create new text that is not exactly the same as any existing text. For example, if you ask Bard to write a poem, it will generate a poem that is unique and original, even though it may draw inspiration from other poems.

Ultimately, whether or not you consider Bard to be a creator of the new and novel is a matter of opinion. However, I believe that Bard is a powerful tool that can be used to create new and original content, even if it does not meet the strict definition of "novel" under US patent law.

You:

session-moses > moses < | Bard-rs bard-rs > Moses Moses 10:57 03-Jun-23

These conversations with AI on our *NSF Proposal* will be memorialized at an '*internal register*'. Those that are not fundamental to the building of our NSF Proposal, are not non-obvious, nor novel will be published at <https://bit.ly/EJM> (Updated 20240308)

An interim document, a concept page for our *NSF Proposal* was sent to *Racial Equity in STEM Education (EHR Racial Equity)*, ehrraciaequitypd@nsf.gov. It resulted in a 10th of October 2023 conference call with an NSF guide. We were lifted to push on to the **October 8, 2024** Proposal deadline.

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We have the following hosting sites for our Proposal work: EnvironmentalJusticeMatters.org, and UnThinkableIdeas.org; we have not hosted our Proposal here during the NSF preparation to avoid any suggestion we are extending our Proposal into space beyond our Proposal Document. We are building a brand around a core issue; the risk of danger includes exposure to Air Pollution. The danger is to Public Health, the health of Flora and Fauna, and the Climate. I(KM) trademarked '*Climate Protection Fund*', created the NYS not-for-profit corporation '*Climate Protection Fund Inc.*', *Federal Unique Entity ID: YKQUK1UC1JQ3*, domains ClimateProtectionFund.world, and

ClimateProtectionFund.eu. The domains are to be built, the restriction being not building beyond the NSF Proposal during construction of the Proposal. Why choose '.eu' > one of the guiding lights for our interventions includes the European Union's *Precautionary Principle*. We are presenting *Environmental Justice Matters* as a project of the *Climate Protection Fund Inc.*

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- Our Archive entries:
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K Moses

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